

Catalytic Oxidation of Toluene in the Vapour Phase.

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Toluene may be oxidised in the vapour phase to benzaldehyde, benzoic acid or carbon dioxide and water according to conditions and nature of catalysts used. The reactions taking place may be represented by the following equations :

Traces of anthraquinone may also be formed but the amount being very small, it is left out of consideration in this work. It is evident from the above equations that low temperature and excess of oxygen will favour the formation of carbonic acid, high temperature and less oxygen will favour aldehyde formation, while moderate temperature will be necessary for benzoic acid. It will be seen from the experimental data that this is actually the case, though very high temperature and prolonged contact with the catalyst favour complete combustion of toluene.

Different catalysts have been used by different investigators for the partial combustion of toluene and other aromatic hydrocarbons. Thus, metallic platinum was used by Coquilon (*Compt. rend.*, 1875 80, 1089), and by Wood and others (*ibid.*, 1907, 145, 127). Oxides of nickel and cobalt were also found useful (F. P. 379725, 1907) while oxide of vanadium either alone or mixed with molybdenum trioxide and other oxides was found particularly suitable by Walter (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1892, 45, 107) Gibbs (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1919, 11, 1031) and others, while Maxted (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1928, 47, 431) used tin vanadate as catalyst. Various catalysts have been used in these investigations and satisfactory results have been obtained with tin vanadate, specially when mixed with silica gel, alumina or active carbon.

In carrying out the oxidation, the following procedure was adopted. The reaction tube consisting of a glass combustion tubing ($2\frac{3}{5}' \times 1''$), packed in the middle with about 10 c.c. of the catalyst in the form of small porous granules, was heated in an electric furnace, the temperature of which was regulated by a rheostat and noted with a thermometer with a bulb placed in the catalyst bed. Air freed from carbon dioxide was passed with the help of a Cenco blower after dividing it into two sections, primary and secondary, each being measured separately with the flowmeter. The quantity of air was controlled by regulating the speed of the motor and by means of pinch-cocks placed on the passage. The flask containing a constant volume of toluene was heated in a thermostat, the primary air passed through the flask and laden with toluene vapour entered the reaction chamber. Just before entrance into the reaction tube, the toluene laden primary air was mixed with secondary air, heated in an oil-bath. The tube connecting the flask and the reaction tube was coiled with nicrom wire and heated electrically to prevent condensation of toluene vapour.

The products of oxidation were led through a test tube constricted at the centre and plugged with glass wool and perforated at the closed end. Benzoic acid collected in the constricted portion of the tube while benzaldehyde and carbonic acid passed through the perforations and were absorbed by standard baryta solution. Benzaldehyde was estimated in this solution by the addition of KHSO_3 (Sutton, "Volumetric Analysis", p. 311) while carbonic acid was estimated from the precipitate consisting of barium carbonate with the help of Schroedter apparatus. Benzoic acid deposited in the constricted tube was estimated by extraction with neutral rectified spirit and titration with alkali. When the rate of flow of toluene vapour was rather fast, a small portion of benzoic acid passed out and dissolved in the baryta solution. This portion of benzoic acid was estimated by titrating the clear baryta solution with hydrochloric acid.

The quantity of toluene passing through the reaction tube was obtained from the difference in the weight of the flask containing toluene before and after each experiment.

The preparation of the catalysts and their incorporation with supports are dealt with later. Only pure Kahlbaum chemicals were used for the purpose.

Study of Nickel Catalysts.

Nickel oxide.—As very meagre practical details of the work of Wood, who obtained small quantities of benzaldehyde from toluene with nickel oxide as catalyst, are available we re-investigated the catalytic properties of nickel oxide.

A solution of pure nickel nitrate was precipitated with excess of pure caustic soda which was added very slowly with constant stirring. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with distilled water and dried at 110° and made into a large number of small pills in the moist state by application of minimum pressure between the fingers, so that the pills might retain a loose spongy structure. The pills were then packed between asbestos fibres and dried at 200°. It will be seen from the experimental data given in the following table that nickel oxide is not very active below 280°, the yield of benzaldehyde is fairly good but that of benzoic acid very poor. As is to be expected, the yield of benzaldehyde rises with temperature and liberal supply of air.

TABLE I a.

Catalyst—Nickel oxide. Volume of the catalyst space = 10.5 c.c.
Temp. of thermostat = 45°. Temp. of the secondary air = 70°.

Run No.	Temp.	Space Velocity.		Products on toluene used.		
		Primary air.	Secondary air.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂
1	290°	300	800	2%	6.3%	...
2	320	400	1000	3.1	7.2	4.8%
3	320	500	1200	4.3	7.8	3.4
4	320	500	1500	6.9	7.6	2.9
5	320	800	1700	5.8	7.9	1.8

TABLE I b.

Values calculated from data of Table Ia.

Run No.	Toluene attacked.	Products on toluene attacked.			
		Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂	Toluene destroyed.
2	10.03 %	31 %	72 %	48 %	14.4 %
3	11.03	39.1	70.9	30.9	9.2
4	12.66	54	59.8	22.8	6.84
5	11.6	50	68.1	11.2	3.36

Run number gives the number of successive runs with the same catalyst and indicates the efficiency of a catalyst on continued use.

Space velocity :—The velocity of all air currents is expressed as space velocity, namely, c.c. per hour per c.c. of the catalyst space.

(b) *Metallic nickel mounted on alumina.*—A mixed solution of pure nickel and aluminium nitrates was precipitated with excess of caustic soda, washed thoroughly and dried at 120°. 20 G. of these materials in the form of pills were packed between asbestos fibre and reduced in a current of hydrogen for about 24 hours.

It will be noted from Table II that yields of benzoic acid and benzaldehyde are not satisfactory when the rate of flow is increased. Toluene passes through the catalyst layer unoxidised, while too low a velocity causes complete combustion.

TABLE II.

Catalyst—Metallic nickel mounted on alumina. Volume of the catalyst space = 10 c.c. Temp. of toluene bath = 50°. Temp. of the secondary air = 75°.

Temp.	Primary air.	Secondary air.	Benzoic acid on toluene used.
280°	500	1100	2.5 %
290	200	500	7.5
290	500	1100	3.5
300	200	500	9.1
330	200	500	8.9
330	200	500	8.9

(c) *Partly reduced nickel oxide.*—The oxide was prepared in the usual manner, dried at 110° and reduced in a current of hydrogen at 310°. It was found that little improvement was attained by reduction of the oxide for 15 hours but much better results were obtained by partial reduction of nickel oxide in a slow current of hydrogen for 3 to 4 hours only.

It appears that the presence of small amount of lower oxide of nickel is favourable for catalysis. It was apprehended that the lower oxide would be easily oxidised to the higher state in the presence of air and the activity of the catalyst would suffer but as the figures for repeated runs will show (Table III a), this apprehension has proved groundless. Once the reaction is started, the lower oxide is evidently reformed by the oxidation of toluene vapour.

TABLE III a.

Catalyst—Nickel oxide reduced in a slow current of hydrogen for 3 to 4 hours at 310°. Volume of the catalyst space = 10.1 c.c. Temp. of the thermostat = 45°. Temp. of the secondary air = 70°.

Run No.	Temp.	Space velocity		Products on toluene used.		
		Prim. air.	Sec. air.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .
1	290°	300	800	5.2%	11.7%	5.9%
2	290	800	1700	10.8	8.1	2.4
3	320	800	1700	11.8	8.9	9.1
4	„	1000	2500	16.8	10.2	0.05
5	340	„	„	20	13.1	0.12
6	„	1500	3500	18.9	12.1	„
7	420	1500	3500	10.1	16.1	8.6
8	450	1500	3500	9.6	18.1	14.9
9	450	„	„	8.2	17.6	14.1
10	„	1000	2500	5.7	15.9	17.4

TABLE III b.

Products on toluene attacked.

Run No.	Toluene attacked.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .	Toluene destroyed.
1	15.85 %	35.2 %	73.6 %	30.8 %	9.24 %
2	15.87	67.9	50.9	15	4.5
4	21.624	77.8	47.2	0.2	0.06
5	26.75	74.6	48.8	0.4	0.12
7	27.984	36	57.5	30.7	9.21
8	24.417	39.3	74.2	61	18.3
10	28.328	24.4	68.2	74.6	22.8

(d) *Partly reduced nickel oxide mounted on alumina.*—Still better results were obtained by incorporation of slightly reduced nickel oxide with small quantities of alumina. The activity of the nickel-alumina catalysts, however, varied according to the proportion of nickel and aluminium. From a solution of nitrates nickel and aluminium were precipitated with caustic soda, washed carefully and dried at 110°. It was then reduced in a current of hydrogen for 3½ hours at 310° and cooled in a current of hydrogen. It was found that the presence of 10—20 % alumina in a mixed catalyst gave the most satisfactory results. By varying the temperature either the acid or the aldehyde could be obtained in good yields. The lower temperature (320—40°) is favourable for acid formation while higher temperature (420—50°) is suitable for the formation of aldehyde. The difference of 100° is great enough to allow regulation of temperature to obtain either the acid or the aldehyde as the main product. In the following Table IV a the data obtained with only one alumina-nickel catalyst are given though several such mixtures were tried as catalysts.

TABLE IV a.

Catalyst—20% alumina and 80% partly reduced nickel oxide. Volume of the catalyst space=10.2 c.c. Temp. of the thermostat=50°. Temp. of the secondary air=70°.

Run No.	Temp.	Space velocity		Products on toluene used		
		Prim. air.	Sec. air.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .
1	295°	600	1500	14.2 %
2	295	500	1000	14.3
3	300	1200	2500	18.3
4	320	1500	3000	23.7
5	320	1200	2500	20.8
6	340	1500	3100	33.1	8.3 %	...
7	340	31.4	7.9	0.2 %
8	420	14.8	12.4	14.3
9	450	9.9	12.9	18.3

TABLE IV b.

Run No.	Products on toluene attacked				
	Toluene attacked.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .	Toluene destroyed.
6	32.046 %	103.4 %	26 %
7	30.483	102.9	25.9	0.6 %	0.18 %
8	26.178	56.4	47.3	54.5	16.35
9	24.138	41.2	58.7	76.2	22.8

Study of Vanadium Catalysts.

(a) *Aluminium vanadate.*—In view of the encouraging result obtained by mounting partly reduced nickel oxide on alumina, we applied this support to the well known catalyst vanadium pentoxide whose high activity has already been referred to.

To a solution of pure aluminium nitrate an excess of a solution of sodium vanadate was slowly added with constant stirring. The precipitate was washed, thoroughly dried at 110° and formed into porous globules. It will be observed that the yield of either the acid or the aldehyde is not up to expectation.

TABLE V a.

Catalyst—Aluminium vanadate. Volume of the catalyst space = 11.6 c. c. Temp. of the thermostat = 50°. Temp. of the secondary air = 65°.

Temp.	Space velocity.		Yield of products on toluene used		
	Prim. air.	Sec. air.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .
280°	200	500	26.02 %	4.8 %	1.1 %
"	"	"	18.8	4.1	1.8
320	"	"	20.4	8.3	4.1
"	"	"	19.2	8.6	8.9
380	200	500	23.8	10.3	4.3
350	300	700	24.8	4.2	1.3
380	400	900	24.4	10.8	2.1
450	"	"	8.5	11.2	8.7
"	1000	2500	8.9	11.8	0.56

TABLE V b.

Toluene used.	Products on toluene attacked			Toluene destroyed.
	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .	
19.5%	102.6%	24.6%	5.1%	1.51%
23.7	86	35.4	17.3	5.19
23.05	83.4	37.8	16.96	5.088
28.1	85	36.9	15.8	4.59
17.23	49.4	65.2	21.7	6.51
22.64	109.7	18.5	5.7	1.67

(b) *Vanadium pentoxide incorporated with silica gel.*—Hydrochloric acid (*d* 1.05) was added drop by drop to a concentrated solution of sodium silicate with mechanical stirring. After washing, the precipitate was incorporated with a solution of ammonium vanadate and rubbed well in a mortar. It was dried first on water-bath and finally at 110° and was used in the form of small porous balls. It will be observed from Table VI a that the results are more promising than any obtained previously. A maximum of 41.2% benzoic acid is obtained at 290°, the rate of flow of primary air being 200 and secondary air 500. On raising the temperature and the rate of flow of primary and secondary air, benzaldehyde is obtained in large amounts. Reduction of the rate of flow favours complete combustion.

TABLE VI a.

Catalyst—Silica gel and vanadium oxide. Volume of the catalyst space = 10.6 c.c. Temp. = 50°. Temp. of the secondary air = 75°.

Run No.	Temp.	Space velocity.		Yield of products on toluene used		
		Prim. air.	Sec. air.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .
1	280°	200	500	38 %	2.8%	8.3%
2	290°	200	500	41.2	3	8.9
3	290°	500	1500	26	7.9	3.1
4	290°	200	500	40.1	3.2	9.0
1	320°	200	500	37.9	3.1	10.9
2	320°	600	1200	32.8	6.4	5.2
3	430°	600	1200	10.3	11.2	27.2
4	"	1200	2500	8.7	15.9	10.1
5	"	1200	2400	8.3	15.1	8.9
6	"	1200	2400	8.9	14.6	9.1
7	"	200	500	1.2	3.8	50.6

TABLE VI b.

Run No.	Toluene attacked.	Products on toluene attacked			Toluene destroyed.
		Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .	
2	36·17%	113·8%	8·2%	24·5%	7·35%
3	35·55	112·6	8·9	25·2	7·54
1	34·38	110·1	9·0	31·7	6·51
2	31·728	103·4	20·18	16·4	4·92
3	25·62	40·2	43·7	106·2	31·26
4	19·386	6·2	19·5	260·8	78·0

(c) *Tin vanadate as catalyst.*—To a solution of tin chloride a solution of sodium vanadate was added slowly till precipitation was complete. The product was thoroughly washed, dried at 110° and was used in the form of porous pills. The results prove the high activity of tin vanadate, a maximum of about 45% benzoic acid having been obtained.

The yield of aldehyde was 14·1% at 450°. The difference of temperature is, therefore, sufficiently great to regulate the yield of either benzoic acid or benzaldehyde. If the rate of flow is moderate, complete combustion to carbon dioxide takes place at this high temperature.

TABLE VII a.

Catalyst—Tin vanadate. Volume of the catalyst space = 10·6 c.c.
Temp. of the thermostat = 45°. Temp. of the secondary air = 75°.

Run No.	Temp.	Space velocity		Yield of benzoic acid on toluene used.
		Prim air.	Sec. air.	
1	270°	200	500	25%
2	..	300	800	17
3	..	200	500	23
4	280	200	500	40·4
5	290	200	500	45
6	290	500	1100	36
7	..	200	500	44·2
8	..	200	500	45·1

TABLE VII b.

Run No.	Temp.	Space velocity		Yield of products on toluene used		
		Prim. air.	Sec. air.	Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .
6	320°	200	400	20.2%	4.2%	28.3%
7	"	900	2000	18.3	6.84	12.6
8	380°	"	"	9.7	9.3	25.8
9	420°	"	"	8.4	11.6	30.5
10	450°	"	"	1.6	12.3	36.5
11	"	1200	1500	1.95	13.8	20.01
12	"	1500	3500	2.2	14.1	9.2
13	"	200	500	nil	6.3	48.3

TABLE VII c.

Run No.	Toluene attacked.	Products on toluene attacked			Toluene destroyed.
		Benzoic acid.	Benzaldehyde.	CO ₂ .	
6	27.29%	73.99%	15.5%	103.6%	31.08%
7	23.45	77.8	29.1	54.7	16.41
8	23.106	42.1	40.4	112.1	33.63
9	25.542	32.9	41.5	119.6	35.58
10	22.85	6.9	53.7	159.4	47.8
12	16.67	13.1	84.4	55	16.5
13	19.97	...	31.5	241.5	72.45

Tin vanadate mounted on silica gel.—The activity of tin vanadate could be further increased by mounting it on silica gel. To a concentrated solution of sodium silicate, hydrochloric acid (d 1.05) was added drop by drop with constant stirring. The silica gel obtained was carefully washed and suspended in a solution of tin chloride and a solution of sodium vanadate was added until tin vanadate was completely precipitated and incorporated with silica gel. The mixed precipitate was used in the form of porous ball as usual,

TABLE VIII a.

Catalyst—20% silica gel and 80% tin vanadate. Volume of the catalyst space=10.7 c.c. Temp. of the thermostat=45°. Temp. of the secondary air=70°. Temp. of the reaction=295°.

Run No.	Space velocity		Yield of benzoic acid on toluene used.
	Prim. air.	Sec. air.	
1	200	500	50.9%
2	"	"	56.1
3	"	"	57.8
4	"	"	55.9
5	"	800	40.1
6	"	1200	34.8

TABLE VIII b.

Catalyst—10% silica gel and 90% tin vanadate. Volume of the catalyst space=10.6 c.c. Temp. of the thermostat=45°. Temp. of the reaction=295°.

Run No.	Space velocity		Yield of benzoic acid on toluene used.
	Prim. air.	Sec. air.	
1	200	500	52%
2	200	500	56
3	200	500	55.1
4	300	2000	32.3

TABLE VIII c.

Catalyst—50% tin vanadate and 50% silica gel. Volume of the catalyst space=10.8 c.c. Temp. of the thermostat=45°. Temp. of the reaction=295°.

Run No.	Space velocity		Yield of benzoic acid on toluene used.
	Prim air.	Sec. air.	
1	200	500	14%
2	200	500	16
3	200	500	18.1
4	200	500	15.3
5	300	1000	10.6

TABLE VIII *d.*

Catalyst—30% tin vanadate and 70% silica gel. Volume of the catalyst space=10.3 c.c. Temp. of the thermostat=45°. Temp. of the reaction=295°.

Run No.	Space velocity		Yield of benzoic acid on toluene used.
	Prim air.	Sec. air.	
1	200	500	6.1%
2	200	500	5
3	200	500	7
4	200	500	5.8

From the above experimental data, it will be clear that highly porous alumina and silica serve more as promoters than as mere supports for nickel and vanadium catalysts. The activities are higher than those calculated from the composition of the constituents on the supposition that the activity of one is independent of the other. The efficiency of vanadium oxide and tin vanadate can be increased by addition of a small amount of silica gel, while the activity of partly reduced nickel oxide can similarly be increased by the addition of small amounts of alumina. This is particularly significant as nickel catalyst is comparatively cheap and the activity of mixed nickel alumina catalyst is considerable though not equal to that of vanadium catalyst.